

IMPROVING USE OF REMOTE BANKING SERVICES IN UZBEKISTAN

Sobirov Ilxom Husanovich

Samarkand State University of Architecture Construction,
Associate Professor of the " Economics " Department

***Abstract:** The article shows the problems of the development of digital banking in Uzbekistan, as well as specific recommendations*

***Keywords:** Digital Bank, interactive analysis, remote banking product*

Introduction

"Strategy for the reform of the banking system of the Republic of Uzbekistan for 2020-2025" approved by the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated March 2, 2020 No. .

The document defines the goals, tasks and priority areas of the development of the banking system, the directions of transformation and reform of the banking system in 2020 - 2025, ways to search for possible solutions based on the experience of transforming the financial sector of foreign countries and taking into account world trends in the financial sector. Effective ways of improving the quality of banking services in commercial banks have been determined.

Mobile banking is the most advanced and popular method of providing new banking services by commercial banks. Mobile banking is a modern way of using banking services through a mobile phone (smartphone) using the Internet. This method allows users of banking services to manage their bank account remotely and provides almost all internet banking operations.

With the help of mobile banking, the client has the following options:

- monitor the status of bank cards (credit, debit, etc.);
- mobile and landline phone services,
- making payments for internet providers, utility, cable and digital television services without intermediary fees;
- conducting online conversion practices;
- making transfers from card to card;
- setting up automatic execution of transactions - payments on account or on certain dates;
- getting information about the receipt of funds in the bank account;
- get information about the transactions made through a bank card;
- making purchases in online stores;
- extinguish loans,
- adding funds to deposits;
- getting a loan;
- receiving and sending money transfer;
- Paying YHXBB fines;
- opening a bank card;
- blocking and unblocking a bank card;
- payment of interest on deposits to a bank card;
- extending the validity period of the bank card;

- making international money transfers in different currencies through the mobile application.

To use mobile banking services, the client must first open a bank account, that is, a card account (bank card). For this, it is necessary to visit the bank (or remotely), fill out the necessary documents, and download the corresponding application to the mobile phone via the Internet..

Mobile applications may be offered by banks or payment organizations. If the mobile application and the bank card belong to the same bank, it is possible to be exempted from small brokerage fees when carrying out transactions through this application. For example, there are commissions for transferring funds from one card to another or withdrawing cash. In general, the commission does not exceed 1%.

If the application is installed on the smartphone, it is enough to go through authorization in this application with a bank card, that is, it is necessary to enter the information requested about the bank card in the application..

For authorization, it is necessary to enter the information on the front of the card (name of the card holder, individual card number and card validity period). Then it is necessary to confirm the increased authorization using the code received by the bank's SMS message. After that, it is important to set a password (PIN code) to access the application and remember it, in case of theft or loss of the phone, the security of funds is provided by this password.

Multiple cards can be registered in one application. This allows you to easily switch from one card to another in the application itself and make a payment with the desired card.

Each mobile banking app has a different design and menu, but that's not a problem because they're so easy to use. The menu consists mainly of sections according to the operations desired by the user (transfers, payments, etc.). First of all, you need to enter the card information in the application, after which you can make payments.

As soon as you perform any banking operation through mobile banking, an SMS message about the operation will be sent to the phone number registered in the application.

Advantages of mobile banking:

- Using banking services remotely through a mobile application;
- Saving time;
- Works 24 hours a day.

Disadvantages of mobile banking:

- Theft or loss of a mobile phone;
- Low level of account security.

The Decree of the President of May 12, 2020 on the "Strategy for the reform of the banking system of the Republic of Uzbekistan for the years 2020-2025" also requires the careful adoption of modern technologies to establish remote banking services, the identification of new types of services and products, studying foreign best practices and increasing the popularity of banking services in our country. use, protection of consumer rights, increasing the financial literacy of the population is given special importance to be among the current issues of our time. Therefore, this decision started a new stage in the development of banking services.

REFERENCES

1. Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated May 12, 2020 No. PF-5992 on "Strategy for reforming the banking system of the Republic of Uzbekistan for 2020-2025".
2. Innovative management: ucheb. [Text] / pod ed. S.D. Ilenkova. - M.: Yuniti, Banki birji, 2001. - 321 p.
3. Gaibnazarova Z.T. Modernization: upravlenie innovation I upravlencheskie innovation. XIX International conference "History of management and business. Upravlencheskiy trud i roli menedzherov: proshloe, nastoyashchee, budushchee", MGU named M.V. Lomonosova, Russia, Moscow. September 21-22, 2018. S. 79-88
4. Baryutin L.S. Upravlenie tekhnicheskimi novovvedeniyami v promyshlennosti. - L.: Izd-vo LGU, 1986. - 12 p.
5. Concept of the development strategy of the Republic of Uzbekistan until 2035. <https://kun.uz/news/2019/05/18/uzbekistan's-development-by-2035-concept>
6. Concept of social and economic complex development of the Republic of Uzbekistan until 2030. <https://sputniknews-uz.com/20191113/Uzbekistan-by-2030-social-economic-development-concept-tayrlandi-12788459.html>